

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEAMWORK SKILLS AND WORK VALUES OF TEACHERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 10

Pages: 1027-1037

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2029

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12725814

Manuscript Accepted: 06-15-2024

The Mediating Effect of Teaching Effectiveness in the Relationship between Teamwork Skills and Work Values of Teachers

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Abstract

The main thrust of the study was to find out the mediating effect of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between teamwork skills and the work values of teachers in public schools. This study employed a non-experimental quantitative design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique. This study was conducted in Alabel 3 District, Division of Sarangani for the school year 2022-2023. Based on the results, the level of teaching effectiveness was high in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development, while neither agree nor disagree. In terms of plus factors. The level of teamwork skills was high in terms of communication, time management, problem-solving, listening, critical thinking, collaboration, and leadership. The extent of the work values of teachers was observed all the time in terms of strong work ethics, responsibility, integrity, honesty, reliability, adaptability, accountability, and self-motivation. There was a significant relationship between teamwork skills and work values, teamwork skills and teaching effectiveness, and teaching effectiveness and work values. Lastly, teaching effectiveness on the relationship between teamwork skills and work values was significant but partial.

Keywords: *educational management, teaching effectiveness, teamwork skills, work values, mediating effect*

Introduction

Several global issues have impacted teachers' work values, including the shortage of qualified teachers, technological advancements, inadequate compensation, diverse student populations, and political interference. The shortage of teachers result in overworked teachers who may feel undervalued and unsupported. At the same time, technological advancements require teachers to adapt to new teaching methodologies and be more tech-savvy. Inadequate compensation demotivate teachers and lead to high turnover rates, affecting the quality of education students provide. Diverse student populations require teachers to be culturally sensitive and adaptable to different learning styles. Political interference in education can lead to a lack of academic freedom and a decline in the quality of education provided. These issues impact the work values of teachers and their ability to provide quality education to their students (Kim et al., 2019).

On the other hand, the work values of teachers are essential as they shape the quality of education provided to students. Effective teachers have strong work values, such as a love for teaching, a commitment to life-long learning, and a dedication to student achievement. Educators who emphasize cooperation, innovation, and creativity are more suited to satisfy their students' different requirements and provide an engaging and exciting learning environment. Additionally, teachers with high ethical standards and integrity are likelier to build trust with students and create a positive school culture. In short, the work values of teachers play a crucial role in student's success and the overall quality of education (Podolsky et al., 2019; Wilcha, 2020).

However, a different aspect that the researcher thought was intriguing is teamwork skills. High-fidelity simulation has become a popular way to teach collaborative skills in high-risk fields like aviation, healthcare, and nuclear power generation. Unfortunately, the phrases simulation and high-fidelity simulation are frequently used interchangeably in training, which could be better because it overemphasizes instructional technology. The authors present a typology of simulation fidelity and refute the ideas that more simulation fidelity leads to more effective training, and that simulation fidelity is one-dimensional (Martínez et al., 2022; Valtonen et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2019).

In the Philippines, the work values of teachers are affected by several issues, including inadequate compensation, heavy workload, limited access to professional development opportunities, political interference, and limited access to technology. These issues can result in demotivated and overworked teachers who may need more resources and support to provide quality education to their students. The lack of professional development opportunities can lead to a stagnant work environment. At the same time, political interference can create a lack of academic freedom and a decline in the quality of education provided. The limited access to technology can also make it challenging for teachers to stay up-to-date with the latest teaching methodologies. These issues can impact the work values of teachers in the Philippines and the quality of education provided to their students.

Research Objectives

Specifically, this research study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. To measure the level of teaching effectiveness in terms of:
 - 1.1. content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 1.2. learning environment;

- 1.3. curriculum and planning;
- 1.4. assessment and reporting;
- 1.5. personal growth and professional development; and
- 1.6. plus factor.
2. To describe the level of teamwork skills in terms of:
 - 2.1. communication;
 - 2.2. time-management;
 - 2.3. problem-solving;
 - 2.4. listening;
 - 2.5. critical thinking;
 - 2.6. collaboration; and
 - 2.7. leadership.
3. To ascertain the extent of work values of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. strong work ethics;
 - 3.2. responsibility;
 - 3.3. integrity;
 - 3.4. honesty;
 - 3.5. reliability;
 - 3.6. adaptability;
 - 3.7. accountability; and
 - 3.8. self-motivation.
4. What are their reflections about teaching as their present career?
 - 4.1. work values and teamwork skills;
 - 4.2. work values and teaching effectiveness; and
 - 4.3. teaching effectiveness and teamwork skills.
5. To determine the significance of mediation of teaching effectiveness on teamwork skills and work values.

Methodology

This study employed the quantitative non-experimental approach, using a correlation technique to measure the association between passion and commitment. Descriptive non-experimental correlational design controls the degree to which one variable is related to another or more variables (Bueno, 2019). In this study, the correlation method is the best strategy to achieve this study's goals and find out whether the hypothesis is accepted. H_0 is born, and H_a is accepted if the significance value exceeds 0.5. Hypothesis testing determines whether the correlations are strong or weak (Creswell, 2012).

Further, the researcher may examine the characteristics, behaviors, and experiences of the study participants because it is a fact-finding investigation (Wang et al., 2020). The descriptive study assessed teachers' levels of teaching effectiveness, teamwork, and work values in Sarangani Province, Region XII. It is correlational since it investigated the relationship between variables such as teaching effectiveness, Teamwork, and teachers' work values, using the survey questionnaire to gather the primary data.

The study was conducted in Alabel, one of the municipalities in Sarangani, Region XII, Philippines, from January to February 2022 among Public School Teachers in Alabel 3 District. It was conducted in 9 public schools in Alabel 3 District. Alabel is a first class and capital municipality of the Province of Sarangani. It is 166 radial kilometers South of Davao City and 15 radial kilometers East of General Santos City. It can be reached by taking a thirty-minute ride on any public transport vehicle from General Santos City airport or catching a public jeepney or multi cabs going to Poblacion and other neighboring barangays of Alabel.

In addition, Alabel is strategically located on the eastern side of the Province of Sarangani, bounded on the North by the Municipality of Malungon, on the South and East by the Municipality of Malapatan, and on the west by the City of General Santos and Sarangani Bay. Also, Alabel is divided into four school districts: Alabel 1 District, Alabel 2 District, Alabel 3 District, and Alabel 4 District. Moreover, the schools in Alabel 3 District are currently implementing the K to 12 education curricula of the Department of Education.

The study's respondents were 269 public school teachers from 9 different schools in the municipality of Alabel, Alabel 3 District, Division of Sarangani, during the school year 2022-2023. Every participant was given an equal chance to be included in the study and to get a sample frame of the distribution of replies using a stratified random sampling strategy with proportionate allocation. Slovin's Formula was used to determine the appropriate number of the sample selected at random.

Inclusion criteria for respondents in this study were established to ensure the relevance and sustainability of the sample. Firstly, public school teachers from diverse backgrounds were included to capture various perspectives. Secondly, respondents needed to have a maximum of three years of teaching experience to ensure adequate professional expertise. Thirdly, individuals with varying levels of job satisfaction, as assessed by a validated instrument, were included to explore the relationship between workplace spirituality. Lastly, respondents were required to have experience in their teaching environment to investigate the mediating effect of professional commitment on the relationship above.

Exclusion criteria were established to maintain the study's focus and integrity. Firstly, private school teachers were excluded as the research specifically targeted public school teachers' contexts. Secondly, teachers with less than three years of experience were excluded to ensure adequate professional competence and familiarity with the teaching environment. Lastly, respondents with no prior experience or limited interaction with their teaching environment were excluded as the study aimed to examine the mediating effect of professional commitment in the relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality among public school teachers.

Withdrawal criteria addressed potential ethical concerns and protected the respondents' well-being. Respondents had the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without providing a reason. Additionally, respondents who experienced any distress or discomfort during the data collection process were allowed to withdraw without consequence. Strict confidentiality measures were employed to ensure that participants' identities and responses were kept anonymous, further promoting safety and privacy throughout the study.

The necessary data was gathered using a systematic procedure. After developing a research questionnaire, the researcher sought validation from experts in the field to ensure its accuracy and effectiveness. Once the validation process was completed and the necessary revisions were made, the researcher submitted an application letter outlining the study protocol to the Ethics and Review Committee. Following a thorough application review, the committee approved the research to proceed. With the approval in hand, the researcher then sent a letter to the Dean of the Graduate School, notifying them of the study and seeking any additional guidance or support as needed. Subsequently, the researcher requested authorization to conduct the study in writing from the Superintendent of the School Division of the Department of Education in Sarangani Division.

Additionally, the researcher submitted a second letter to the Alabel-3 district supervisor of the many schools that were the subject of this study, requesting permission to conduct the survey among the teachers at each school and then use the Informed Consent Form to explain the findings. After approval, the public school instructors were given survey questionnaires.

One week following the distribution, the researcher physically collected the surveys to give the respondents ample opportunity to reply. All of the issued surveys were collected in total. After that, the completed results were verified and totaled. After the data's totalization, the findings were examined and evaluated in light of the study's objectives.

Validity and Reliability of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire for teamwork skills was modified to fit into the study and will be validated by experts. It has the following indicators: communication, time management, problem-solving, listening, critical thinking, collaboration, and leadership.

The five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used as follows:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.2 - 5.0	Strongly Agree	The level of teamwork skills is very high.
3.4 - 4.1	Agree	The level of teamwork skills is high.
2.6 - 3.3	Moderately Agree	The level of teamwork skills is fairly high.
1.8 - 2.5	Disagree	The level of teamwork skills is low.
1.0 - 1.7	Strong Disagree	The level of teamwork skills is very low.

Further, the questionnaire for work values was modified to fit the study and validated by the experts. It has the following indicators: strong work ethics, responsibility, integrity, honesty, reliability, adaptability, accountability, and self-motivation.

In evaluating the work values of teachers, the four orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used as follows:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.4 - 4.0	Always	The extent of work values is most observed all the time.
2.6 - 3.3	Often	The extent of work values is observed all the time.
1.8 - 2.5	Sometimes	The extent of work values is observed all the time.
1.0 - 1.7	Never	The extent of work values is observed.

Moreover, the questionnaire for teaching effectiveness was adapted from the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers. It was modified to fit the study and subjected to the experts' validation.

The teaching effectiveness questionnaire has the following indicators: content knowledge and pedagogy; learning environment; curriculum and planning; assessment and reporting; personal growth and professional development; and factors.

The following range of means with their descriptions was used to evaluate teachers' teaching effectiveness.

Rating Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.2 - 5.0	Strongly Agree	The level of teaching effectiveness is very high.
3.4 - 4.1	Agree	The level of teaching effectiveness is high.
2.6 - 3.3	Moderately Agree	The level of teaching effectiveness is fairly high.
1.8 - 2.5	Disagree	The level of teaching effectiveness is low
1.0 - 1.7	Strong Disagree	The level of teaching effectiveness is very low.

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Results and Discussion

The Level of Teaching Effectiveness in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Personal Growth and Professional Development, and Factors

Table 1 presents the data on the level of teaching effectiveness in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, personal growth and professional development, and factors. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that content knowledge and pedagogy were high, with a mean of 3.9, which indicated that the teacher's applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas garnered a mean of 4.0. Teachers use various teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills, garnered a mean of 3.8. Teachers apply various teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking; other higher-order thinking skills garnered a mean of 3.9.

Data on learning environments showed that teachers effectively manage classroom structure to engage students in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities in various physical learning environments. It was indicated by the high mean of 3.5 for learning environments. To guarantee that learning-focused classrooms received a mean score of 3.5, teachers employ positive and non-violent punishment to control student conduct constructively. With a mean score of 3.5, teachers address students' gender, needs, abilities, interests, and experiences through diversified, developmentally appropriate learning experiences.

Table 1. *The Level of teaching Effectiveness*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	0.100	3.9	Agree	High
Learning Environment	0.058	3.5	Agree	High
Curriculum and Planning	0.550	3.6	Agree	High
Assessment and Reporting	0.200	4.7	Strongly Agree	Very High
Personal Growth and Professional Development	0.920	3.7	Agree	High
Plus Factor	0.505	3.7	Agree	High
Overall	0.389	3.9	Agree	High

With a mean of 3.6, it was high in curriculum and planning, showing that instructors organize, oversee, and carry out developmentally appropriate teaching and learning procedures to satisfy curricular requirements and various teaching situations. It garnered a mean of 4.0. Teachers participate in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice, garnering a mean of 3.0. Teachers select, develop, organize, and use appropriate teaching-learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals, garnering a mean of 3.9.

In assessment and reporting, data obtained a mean of 4.7, which was interpreted as very high and indicated strongly agreed that teachers design, select, organize, and use diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements garnered a mean of 4.5. Teachers monitor and evaluate learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data garnered a mean of 4.3. Teachers promptly communicate the learners' needs, progress, and achievement to critical stakeholders, including parents/guardians, garnered a mean of 4.1.

The data obtained a mean of 3.7 for personal growth and professional development, which was interpreted as high and indicated that teachers who apply a learner-centered personal philosophy garnered a mean of 3.1. Teachers who set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers scored 4.4.

Data revealed that teaching effectiveness was high in terms of plus factors with a mean of 3.9, which indicated that the teachers perform various related works or activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process, like committee involvement, garnered a mean of 3.5. Advisorship of cocurricular activities garnered a mean of 3.6. Book or journal authorship/contributorship garnered a mean of 4.0. Coordinatorship /chairpersonship garnered a mean of 3.0. Coaching and mentoring learners in competitions garnered a mean of 2.6. Serving as a reliever of classes in the absence of teachers garnered a mean of 2.9. Mentoring pre-service teachers garnered a mean of 2.5. Participation in demonstration teaching garnered a mean of 3.5. Participation as a technical working group member garnered a mean of 3.5.

The Level of Team Work Skills in terms of Communication, Management, Problem-Solving, Listening, Critical Thinking, Collaboration, and Leadership

Table 2 presents the data on the level of teamwork skills in terms of communication, time management, problem-solving, listening, critical thinking, collaboration, and leadership. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that in terms of communicating, problem-solving, and listening, the mean was 3.7, which was interpreted as high, indicating that teachers can impart their insights and thoughts to their colleagues. Teachers exchange information and ideas on essential matters. Teachers always give reports to parents on their children's performance, garnering a mean of 3.8.

Table 2. *The Level of Teamwork Skills*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Communication	0.252	3.7	Agree	High
Time-management	0.321	3.6	Agree	High
Problem-solving	0.252	3.7	Agree	High
Listening	0.252	3.7	Agree	High
Critical Thinking	0.058	3.5	Agree	High
Collaboration	0.200	4.3	Strongly Agree	Very High
Leadership	0.100	3.9	Agree	High
Overall	0.179	3.8	Agree	High

Regarding time management, the data obtained a mean of 3.6, which was interpreted as high, indicating that the teachers can achieve results with optimal use of time and resources, which most of the time garnered a mean of 4.0. Teachers can manage their time doing reports and accomplishments, garnering a mean of 3.5. Teachers can handle their whole class in accomplishing our lessons daily, garnering a mean of 3.4.

In terms of problem-solving, data obtained with a mean of 3.7 was interpreted as high, which indicates that the teachers can examine the root cause of problems and suggest practical solutions. Fostering new ideas garnered a mean of 3.7. Teachers can prioritize and select alternative solutions on certain matters, garnering a mean of 3.5. Teachers can evaluate their learners' capabilities and

performance in class, garnering a mean of 4.0.

In terms of listening, data obtained a mean of 3.7, which was interpreted as high and indicated agreement that the teachers pay attention and acknowledge messages of their superior, which garnered a mean of 4.0. Teachers responding appropriately in discussions garnered a mean of 3.5. Teachers provided feedback and suggestions during our School Learning Assessment Center (SLAC), which garnered a mean of 3.6.

Regarding critical thinking, the data obtained a mean of 3.5, which was interpreted as high and indicated that the teachers ask open-ended questions to ignite their learner's attention. Teachers can analyze their learners' capabilities through performance tests, garnering a mean of 3.5. With a mean score of 3.5, teachers can assess their students' learning, ascertain their requirements, and choose the best time and method for monitoring their development.

Regarding collaboration, data obtained a mean of 4.3, which was interpreted as very high, indicating that teachers strongly agreed that they could apply negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements, which garnered a mean of 4.5. A mean score of 4.3 indicates that teachers can collaborate and cooperate productively with individuals and across companies to fulfill organizational goals and objectives. Teachers can promote collaboration and remove barriers to teamwork and goal accomplishment across the organization, which has garnered a mean of 4.1.

The data regarding leadership yielded a mean score of 3.9, which was considered as vital. Instructors can foster a creative environment and motivate colleagues to develop novel ideas or solutions. A score of 4.0 was reached. The work unit and organization, with a mean score of 3.8, may be improved by teachers applying creative thinking to practical adjustments and solutions. Teachers are capable of coming up with creative ways to complete tasks. They received a mean score of 3.9 for demonstrating resourcefulness and the capacity to achieve with limited resources.

The degree to which teachers uphold strong work ethics, accountability, responsibility, integrity, honesty, dependability, flexibility, and self-motivation

Table 3 presents the data on the extent of work values regarding solid work ethics, responsibility, integrity, honesty, reliability, adaptability, accountability, and self-motivation. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that the extent of work values of teachers was observed all the time in terms of solid work ethics, which obtained a mean of 3.8, which signifies that teachers always consider occupational careers one of the most essential activities in their lives, which garnered a mean of 3.5. Teachers believe that a person is known in society by their work, garnering a mean of 3.8. Teachers believe that one's work provides the best source of achieving perfection in life, which garnered a mean of 4.1.

Table 3. *The Extent of Work Values*

Indicator	SD	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Strong Work Ethics	0.300	3.8	Always	Most observed all the time
Responsibility	0.141	3.9	Always	Most observed all the time
Integrity	0.551	4.1	Always	Most observed all the time
Honesty	0.707	4.2	Always	Most observed all the time
Reliability	0.321	3.6	Always	Most observed all the time
Adaptability	0.300	3.8	Always	Most observed all the time
Accountability	0.265	3.9	Always	Most observed all the time
Self-Motivation	0.361	3.6	Always	Most observed all the time
Overall	0.357	3.9	Always	Observed all the time

In terms of responsibility, data obtained a mean of 3.9, which indicated always and was interpreted as most observed times that the teachers welcome jobs that involve greater responsibility and challenge as they contribute to their learning and growth garnered a mean of 3.8. Teachers usually go to work earlier to prepare for the tasks they have to handle, which garnered a mean of 4.0.

In terms of integrity, data obtained a mean of 4.1, which indicates as always and was interpreted as most observed all the time that the teachers always believe that one should never be late for work unless there is some real emergency garnered a mean of 3.5. They prefer a position where teachers' efforts are valued, garnered a mean of 4.4. Teachers believe that high integrity and mutual respect are essential to cultural understanding, garnered 4.5.

In terms of honesty, the data obtained a mean of 4.2, which indicated that it was always observed and was interpreted as being most observed. Teachers' work can improve the quality of their lives, garnering a mean of 3.7. Teachers are devoted and proud of their work, garnering a mean of 4.7.

Regarding reliability, data obtained a mean of 3.6, which was interpreted as most observed all the time and described as always. Even in this fast-changing world, sincerity, hard work, and integrity remain the golden keys to success in one's work life, which garnered a mean of 3.5. Even if there is no extra pay for working overtime, teachers will still work overtime to finish at night, garnering a mean of 3.5. Teachers demonstrate reliability by accomplishing their tasks at work, which garnered a mean of 3.9.

In terms of adaptability, data obtained a mean of 3.8, describing as always and interpreted as most observed all the time. Teachers believe a job where their co-teachers and they get along well would be ideal, garnered a mean of 4.1. Teachers encourage themselves to cooperate with others and adapt quickly to them, which garnered a mean of 4.4. Teachers demonstrate flexibility and adaptability in their workplace, which garnered a mean of 3.8.

In terms of accountability, the data obtained a mean of 3.9, which was interpreted as most observed all the time and described as always. Teachers' ideal work would allow them to make decisions, garnering a mean of 3.6. Teachers who feel a moral obligation to give a full day's work for a full day's pay garnered a mean of 4.1. Teachers who want to be perfect in their work garnered a mean of 4.0.

In terms of self-motivation, data obtained a mean of 3.6, indicating as always, and was interpreted as most observed all the time. It means that the extent of work values was observed all the time. Teachers believe that a job well done is a reward garnered a mean of 3.5. Teachers believe creating a program for employees is the kind of job they prefer, garnered a mean of 3.3. Teachers believe an opportunity for advancement at work would be ideal, garnering a mean of 4.0.

Significant Relationship between Teamwork Skills and Work Values

Table 4 presents the significant relationship between teamwork skills and work values. Pearson's r was employed to treat the data gathered.

It was discovered that the data were tested at the Alpha level.05 with a df of 159 when the degree of work values and the level of collaboration abilities were combined. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.83, as the table demonstrates. In comparison to the tabular result of 0.159, it was more significant. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. Teachers' work values were strongly impacted by their degree of cooperation abilities and practices.

Table 4. *Significant Relationship between Teamwork and Work Values*

Variables	Df	rxy value n=161		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Teamwork Skills Vs. Work Values	159	0.83	0.159	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship.

Significant Relationship between Teamwork Skills and Teaching Effectiveness

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between teamwork skills and teaching effectiveness. Pearson's r was employed to treat the gathered data.

When the collaboration skills and instructional effectiveness levels were considered, the data were tested at the alpha level.05 with a pdf of 159. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.77, as the table demonstrates. It was more significant than the tabular result of 0.159. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. The efficacy of instructors was shown to be highly impacted by their level of collaborative abilities and practices.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship between Teamwork Skills and Teaching Effectiveness*

Variables	Df	rxy value n=161		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Teamwork Skills Vs. Teaching Effectiveness	159	0.77	0.159	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship.

Significant Relationship between Teaching Effectiveness and Work Values

Table 6 presents the significant relationship between teaching effectiveness and work values. Pearson's r was employed to treat the data gathered.

It was discovered that the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a df of 159 when the work and instructional efficacy levels were considered. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.79, as the table demonstrates. In comparison to the tabular result of 0.159, it was more significant. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. Teachers' job values were highly impacted by their level of performance in the classroom.

Table 6. *Significant Relationship between Teaching Effectiveness and Work Values*

Variables	Df	rxy value n=161		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Teaching Effectiveness Vs. Work Values	159	0.79	0.159	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship.

Mediating Effect of Teaching Effectiveness

Table 7 shows the path analysis of the mediating effect of teaching effectiveness on the relationship between teamwork skills and teachers' work values.

The data revealed the direct effect of teaching effectiveness and teamwork skills, teaching effectiveness and work values, and teamwork skills and work values. Teaching effectiveness and teamwork skills are the paths with an unstandardized regression coefficient of .933, standardized regression coefficient of .798, S.E. of .024, and a probability value of less than 0.05. A low or tiny standard error indicates that the estimate is more accurate, and below the significance level of 0.05 suggests that these two variables have a meaningful association. The influence of efficiency, or effect size, is 97%, which is significant enough to reject the null hypothesis. The route b coefficient—which teaches work values and effectiveness—has a standardized regression coefficient .132, S.E., and an unstandardized regression coefficient of .095, of .043, as well as a p-value of .015, which is below the 0.05 significant alpha threshold. As a result, there is a substantial correlation between work values and the efficacy of instruction. The effect size of teaching effectiveness and work values is 10%.

Lastly, the path c coefficient shows the effect size of teamwork skills and work values. The data result had an unstandardized regression coefficient of .733, or 74% efficiency, a standardized regression coefficient of .790, a computed standard error of .031, and a p-value smaller than 0.05. It indicates that there is a strong correlation between the variables. It provides mathematical evidence favoring the hypothesis that work values and collaboration abilities are related.

Table 7. *Mediating Effect; Path Analysis (Partial Mediation)*

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
Teaching Effectiveness → Teamwork Skills	.933	.798	.024	21.220	***
Teaching Effectiveness → Work Values	.095	.132	.043	3.211	.015
Teamwork Skills → Work Values	.733	.790	.031	14.322	***

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were established: First, the level of teaching effectiveness was high in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, personal growth and professional development, and factor, while very high in term of assessment and reporting. Second, teamwork skills were high in communication, time management, problem-solving, listening, critical thinking, and leadership, while very high in collaboration. Third, the extent of the work values of teachers was most observed all the time in terms of solid work ethics, responsibility, integrity, honesty, reliability, adaptability, accountability, and self-motivation. There was a significant relationship between teamwork skills and work values, teamwork skills and teaching effectiveness, and teaching effectiveness and work values. Lastly, teaching effectiveness on the relationship between teamwork skills and work values was significant but partial.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were established:

Some implications of the study included programs and activities that could teach public educators about teamwork skills, teaching effectiveness, and work values, as these are equally essential variables for better teaching performances in the schools where public educators are employed (Sargiv & Roccas, 2021; Sario & Villocino, 2023).

First, The Department of Education should provide opportunities for staff members to progress their careers within the department, encourage a positive work environment, recognize the role that the profession plays in improving the effectiveness of employee instruction, and conduct focus groups or poll staff members regularly to determine their level of career commitment and identify areas that require improvement. It also should provide opportunities for teachers to develop their teamwork skills and work values through

professional development workshops and training programs. These programs could focus on communication, collaboration, problem-solving, and ethical decision-making.

School administrators could also offer opportunities for team-building activities, particularly at MPRE or year-end events, frequent performance reviews, and chances to engage in cooperative learning to promote social contact. Working on communication, collaboration, alignment, team values, motivation, and anything else that can help a group function as a cohesive unit in the classroom are examples of team-building activities. Maximizing teaching effectiveness should also involve settling disputes, imparting knowledge, or just uniting the group via everyday experiences to result in teaching effectiveness.

Finally, this study could serve as a basis for further research on teacher effectiveness, teamwork skills, and work values. Future research may explore additional variables that could impact these. In addition to evaluating teacher effectiveness and student outcomes, it could also evaluate organizational culture and leadership roles.

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